

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUFUNDA****FIRST NAME: FORTUNATE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 2023 Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. A working hypothesis is.
 - A tentative or plausible answer to a proposed research question in which the researcher sets up a study to find evidence to prove or disprove.¹**
 - A research argument that claims the success of a study.
 - A research argument that shows the failure of a study.

A research argument that shows that the researcher gathered information from various sources.

¹ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations.*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 31.

2. Consulting various literature sources of the existing body of knowledge on a particular topic is fundamental to conducting research to augment, modify or correct it. Consulted sources of information are used in the research writing to support arguments for the research hypotheses or findings. The cited information is listed as references to.

Avoid plagiarism, acknowledge the source of information, and direct readers to the appropriate authority.²

Give credit to the writer for the ability to consult literature widely.

Indicate the number of existing references on the topic of discussion.

Show the writer's ability to use a referencing style guide.

3. When can an author not cite?

When referencing information that is commonly available and has various sources.³

When using signal verbs in a quote.

When the sourced information has been paraphrased.

When sourced data is not from a peer-reviewed journal.

4. A style guide is.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack. Period 1*, Fourth Edition. (Bangui: Euclid University., last modified 2021), 8. Accessed March 18, 2023, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B>.

³ Turabian, *Manual for Writers*, 37.

- A set of rules written to ensure writing consistency, uniformity, and coherence within a publication forum hence making it easy for editors to review content.**⁴
 - Use of rules ensuring language use is varied within a writer's document.
 - The use of rules ensuring punctuation, abbreviations and grammar conventions is varied.
 - Using referencing software such as Zotero in writing to organise references.
5. A writer's storyboard is.
- A plan that outlines the research with several pages where information gathered from various consulted sources and guided by keywords is captured.**⁵
 - A detailed chronology of how the research project is progressing.
 - Stories arise as the study goes on.
 - Reports emerging within a writer's writing group.
6. A research proposal is a written plan of an upcoming project or conference project presentation with the following key elements.
- A problem statement, purpose statement, the research questions the project seeks to answer, a review of existing bodies of knowledge to show what is already known, and methods for data collection and analysis.**⁶
 - Title, summary, and conclusion.

⁴ Turabian, *Manual for Writers*, 41.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 32.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 202.

- Title, outline, conclusion, and references.
 - Title, findings, and conclusion.
7. A Qualitative research design specifies a research approach where the researcher captures participants' experiences and examines how they make sense of the incidents is referred to as.
- A phenomenological approach.**⁷
 - A case study approach.
 - An ethnographic approach.
 - A narrative approach.
8. A qualitative research design will have a philosophical paradigm framework that informs the research. The following paradigm has an ontological stance focusing on the active involvement of participants to construct the reality of a study.
- Transformative.**⁸
 - Social constructivism.
 - Pragmatism.
 - Postpositivist.
9. Which of the following sampling strategy is based on probability and controls for bias?

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 169.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 137.

- Random.**⁹
- Purposive.
- Judgmental.
- Snowballing.

10. To ensure trustworthiness in quantitative and qualitative research quality assurance, which of the following provides validity, credibility, and dependability?

- Triangulation.**¹⁰
- Using only one source of information.
- Reflexivity only.
- Audit trail only.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 440.

¹⁰Phillip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* (lecture, Methodology Related Presentations, National Centre for Academic Dissertation Excellence, YouTube, March 7, 2016) 1.05 min., accessed April 14, 2023,<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

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